

ACRIDINE DERIVATIVES. PART I

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Some 5-substituted 3-amino-6-chloro-acridines have been synthesised for studying their antiseptic properties.

In view of the fact that diaminoacridines possess bactericidal properties (Albert, Francis, Garrod and Linnell, *Brit. J. Exp. Path.*, 1938, 19, 41), it was thought interesting to synthesise acridines with an anilino or halogenated anilino group in position 5 of the general formula (V).

For this purpose *m*-chloroaniline has been condensed with 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid, and 4-nitro-3'-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxylic acid (I), thus formed, is cyclised with phosphorus oxychloride to give two isomeric 5:8-dichloro-3-nitro- and 5:6-dichloro-3-nitroacridines (II and III) out of which only (III) was isolated. To confirm the position of chlorine in the above acridine, an alternative synthesis of 5:8-dichloro-3-nitroacridine (II) has been carried out by condensing *p*-nitroaniline with 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acid to give 4'-nitro-3-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxylic acid which is subsequently cyclised with phosphorus oxychloride. Bradbury and Linnell (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 377) also prepared 4-nitro-3'-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxylic acid in 23% yield by a very tedious method but under our conditions a yield of 60% is obtainable. The yield of the acridine (III) has also been largely improved.

5:6-Dichloro-3-nitroacridine has been further condensed with aniline, *p*-anisidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *m*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline, *o*-bromoaniline, *o*-iodoaniline and 2:3-dichloroaniline. Two of these nitroacridines have been successfully reduced using fused stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid. Reduction with the reagent described by Linnell (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1617) did not yield satisfactory results. The bactericidal properties (against streptococci) of these nitro- and aminoacridines are under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Nitro-3'-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxylic Acid.—*m*-Chloroaniline (2.5 g., 2 mols) was heated with 2.5 g. of 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid at 150-160° for 12 hours. The reaction product was rubbed with dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered and washed well with acetone, when a yellow coloured compound was left. It was crystallised from glacial

acetic acid in bright yellow needles (1.9 g.), m.p. 276°. (Bradbury and Linnell give m.p. 272-73°). (Found: N, 9.74. Calc. for $C_{13}H_9O_4N_2Cl$: N, 9.57 per cent).

4'-Nitro-3-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxylic Acid.—2:4-Dichlorobenzoic acid (1.9 g., 1 mol.), *p*-nitroaniline (2 g. 1.5 mol.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) and 0.1 g. of copper-bronze were powdered and moistened with amyl alcohol (5 c.c.). The whole thing was heated at 140° for 12 hours and amyl alcohol removed by distillation and finally by passing steam. The residue was boiled with additional amount (2 g.) of potassium carbonate and filtered hot. The insoluble potassium salt left on the filter paper was acidified with hot dilute hydrochloric acid and the greenish insoluble mass crystallised from toluene in light yellow flakes (0.48 g.), m.p. 235°. (Found: N, 9.61. $C_{13}H_9O_4N_2Cl$ requires N, 9.57 per cent). The yield could not be improved, though several attempts using nitrobenzene, glycerol, etc. were made.

5:6-Dichloro-3-nitroacridine.—4-Nitro-3'-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxylic acid (4 g.) was heated with phosphorus oxychloride (24 c.c.) at 145-150° for 10 hours. After cooling the excess of phosphorus oxychloride was removed by petroleum ether and the residue treated with 10% ice-cold aqueous ammonia, filtered and left overnight. Next day it was stirred with 20 c.c. of cold acetone, dried and crystallised from benzene when it came out as light yellow flocculant crystals (1 g.), m.p. 201°-202°. (Found: N, 9.64. $C_{13}H_8O_3N_2Cl$, requires N, 9.55 per cent).

5:8-Dichloro-3-nitroacridine.—4'-Nitro-3-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxylic acid (1 g.) was heated with 6 c.c. of phosphorus oxychloride at 110-115° for 45 minutes and at 145° for 10 minutes. The reaction was worked up as above except that after treatment with ice-cold ammonia, it was not left overnight but worked up at once. The acridine of slight greenish yellow colour came out of benzene (2 g.), m.p. 227° (Bradbury and Linnell recorded m.p. 223° for the same isolated from the mixture). (Found: N, 9.75. Calc. for $C_{13}H_8O_3N_2Cl_2$: N, 9.55 per cent).

3-Nitro-6-chloro-5-(p-anisidino) acridine.—5:6-Dichloro-3-nitroacridine (0.5 g.) was heated with *p*-anisidine (0.21 g., 1 mol.) along with phenol (1 g.) at 110-120° for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was triturated with dry ether and filtered when the hydrochloride of the condensation product was obtained in quantitative yield. It was basified with ammonia and crystallised from alcohol in brown powdery crystals, m.p. 264°. (Found: N, 10.86. $C_{20}H_{14}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 11.08 per cent).

3-Nitro-6-chloro-5-(p-chloroanilino) acridine.—The acridine (0.5 g.), heated with molecular quantity (0.21 g.) of *p*-chloroaniline under the above conditions and working up as above, gave the corresponding acridine as yellowish red crystal, m.p. 216-17°. (Found: N, 10.76. $C_{19}H_{13}O_3N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 10.03 per cent).

3-Nitro-6-chloro-5 (2:5-dichloroanilino) acridine.—2:5-Dichloroaniline, when condensed with the same acridine under the above conditions, gave quantitative yield of the hydrochloride of the condensation product which came out as orange flakes after basifying with ammonia and crystallising from alcohol, m.p. 253-55°. (Found: N, 9.88. $C_{18}H_{10}O_3N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 10.03 per cent).

3-Nitro-6-chloro-5 (o-iodoanilino) acridine.—*o*-Iodoaniline; condensed with the acridine under the same conditions, yielded reddish crystals of the corresponding acridine, m.p. 225-26°. (Found: N, 9.17. $C_{19}H_{11}O_3N_2ClI$ requires N 9.17 per cent).

3-Nitro-6-chloro-5 (p-bromoanilino)acridine.—The reaction between bromoaniline (0.31 g.) and dichloronitroacridine (III) proceeded better in toluene (refluxing for 6 hours) than phenol. The reaction was worked up by filtering and washing with ether basifying and crystallising from alcohol, m.p. 214-15°. (Found: N, 9.54. $C_{19}H_{11}O_2N_2ClBr$ requires N, 9.8 per cent).

3-Nitro-6-chloro-5 (o-bromoanilino) acridine.—The acridine (0.5 g.) was directly heated with *o*-bromoaniline (0.3 g., 1 moi.) at 110-120° for 2 hours. The reaction product was worked up by triturating with ether, basifying and crystallising from alcohol and a base, m.p. 245°, was obtained. (Found: N, 10.05. $C_{19}H_{11}O_2N_2Cl$ Br requires N, 9.8 per cent).

3-Nitro-6-chloro-5 (m-chloroanilino) acridine.—The acridine (0.5 g.) was directly heated with molecular amount of *m*-chloroaniline (0.21 g.) at 110-120° for 2 hours. The reaction mixture worked up as above yielded bright red crystals of a base, m.p. 106-107° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.88. $C_{19}H_{11}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 10.94 per cent).

3-Nitro-6-chloro-5 (anilino) acridine.—Aniline when heated with the acridine in molecular proportion under the same conditions yielded the corresponding acridine, m.p. 270°. (Found: N, 12.26. $C_{19}H_{13}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 12.0 per cent).

3-Amino-6-chloro-5(p-bromoanilino)acridine.—3-Nitro-6-chloro-5(*p*-bromoanilino)-acridine (0.5 g.) was suspended in 1.5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 1.5 g. of stannous chloride (powdered) were slowly added with continuous trituration and the whole thing heated on a sand-bath. The tin double salt was collected by suction, dissolved in water (15 c.c.), filtered and basified with a concentrated solution of potassium hydroxide. The base was collected, washed free from alkali, dried and crystallised from benzene in light yellow flakes, m.p. 234-35° (0.2 g.) with previous shrinkage at 229°. (Found: N, 10.16. $C_{19}H_{13}N_2Cl$ Br requires N, 10.52 per cent).

3-Amino-6-chloro-5 (m-chloroanilino) acridine.—3-Nitro-6-chloro-5(*m*-chloroanilino)-acridine (0.5 g.) on reduction as above yielded brownish yellowish flakes of the corresponding amino compound, m.p. 212° with previous shrinkage at 208°. (Found: N, 11.44. $C_{19}H_{13}N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 11.8 per cent).